

First of all, ESP means English for Specific Purpose and moreover, it is usually used and learned for “specific areas” (media, business, chemists, educationalist and so on).

For example, if a student's direction is History, then he or she needs to study ESP. One of the reasons can be that there, a learner studies a certain vocabulary, as most people know: topic-based or context-related terms, like: *Social Structure, Antiquity, Historiography, BCE, CE* and other similar items.

“The basic idea behind ESP is that learners’ needs differ enormously according to future academic or occupational goals, and this is why ESP has become so influential in universities around the world in recent years...”, writes Hyland, K. (2022, p.1). By this, he means who they are going to become in the future makes learners distinct from each other, since their paths of future career are also different.

What is EAP itself?

Journal of English for Academic Purposes (2021) writes that the term EAP (English for Academic Purposes) first invented by Tim Johns in 1974, and described by Hyland, K., Jiang, F. K. (2018) as:

“An approach to language education based on identifying the specific language features, discourse practices, and communicative skills of target academic groups, and which recognizes the subject-matter needs and expertise of learners (2018, pp. 383–384) ...”.

To put it in other words, this approach helps students to understand their knowledge and abilities in General English Language Skills (Listening,

Speaking, Reading and Writing) and specific knowledge, as well as the skills in learners' study field.

Here, it can be seen that mostly, students choose EAP for Academic Communication and Speech, Listening comprehension and Academic Reading, rather than writing or other considerations.

Why do future teachers need to study these?

With the help of the quote by Christina McAuliffe (an American teacher and Woman-astronaut): "I touch the future, I teach.", it is easy to see that being a teacher can actually affect the future of not only children, but the whole country as well. They play an important role in shaping the future. In some cases, the future can actually depend on teachers. If so, individuals who want to become a teacher must understand and accept this job's gravity, then they can decide whether being a teacher is for them or should they choose another path.

After all, becoming an outstanding teacher does require a lot of hard work and discipline. Only if they are ready to understand this concept, are they welcome to be an educator.

Help of EAP and ESP for them

*EAP (English for Academic Purpose) most importantly provides future educators with improved academic language skills. Another reason is that in the classroom, there probably will be learners with different cultures. If a

teacher has studied EAP, he or she hopefully will not have misunderstandings with their students. Because, they know what to expect from different cultures and countries.

Damian F., Tracey C., Parvaneh T. (2022) mentioned that the last few years have significantly modified the ways in which English for Academic Purposes (EAP) is marked and positioned within higher education institutions in the U.K. (Hyland, 2018).

* ESP (English for Specific Purpose)- if a person wants to become a tutor of a particular area, like physics, they will need a bunch of vocabulary which is related to his or her way.

*“Globalization and international development in language education have inspired a shift from the learning of traditional College English to English for Specific Purposes (ESP)”, suggested *Frontiers in Psychology*, AQ Dou, SH Chan, MT Win (2023, p.1).

This means, since the world is changing and improving, requirements for future teachers are also becoming different, more effort-needing.

It is all achievable; just a bit more effort should be put in!

As mentioned earlier, becoming a good teacher is not an easy work: hardworking, studying very deeply, understanding this profession's strength and weight. To achieve it all, ESP and EAP do play a big role. With the help of these two, a student can be a good tutor. That is why ESP and EAP are now being requested from future young educators.

References:

[1] Hyland, K., & Jiang, F. K. (2021). *A bibliometric study of EAP research: Who is doing what, where and when?* *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 49, 100929.

[2] Fitzpatrick, D., Costley, T., & Tavakoli, P. (2022). *Exploring EAP teachers' expertise: Reflections on practice, pedagogy and professional development.* *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 59, 101140.

[3] Dou, A. Q., Chan, S. H., & Win, M. T. (2023). *Changing visions in ESP development and teaching: Past, present, and future vistas.* *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1140659.